

THE IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION ON MEDIA TRANSLATION BETWEEN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

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Abstract: This study explores the influence of globalization on media translation between Uzbek and English, focusing on how global media exchanges have shaped the translation of culture-specific references, idiomatic expressions, and technological advancements. The paper examines the challenges translators face in adapting media content for cross-cultural audiences while preserving the cultural and contextual integrity of the source language. Through a comparative analysis of linguistic borrowing, the tension between domestication and foreignization, and the role of technology in translation processes, the article highlights the critical importance of cultural literacy in media translation. This research provides insights into the growing demand for localized media content in an increasingly globalized world and underscores the evolving role of translators in navigating this dynamic field.

Keywords: globalization, media translation, linguistic borrowing, domestication, foreignization, cross-cultural communication, Uzbek-English translation.

Globalization has significantly influenced how media is produced, consumed, and translated across cultures. Media texts, whether in the form of news, films, or social media content, serve as a crucial medium for cultural interchange and global communication. As global interactions increase, the demand for accurate and culturally relevant translations from Uzbek into English and vice versa has also risen. This article investigates the impact of globalization on media translation practices between Uzbek and English, with a particular emphasis on the challenges that arise when translating cultural references, idiomatic expressions, and technological terminology. Moreover, the research explores the role of technology and linguistic borrowing in media translation, examining how these elements impact cross-cultural communication.

The research methodology for this study involves a qualitative analysis of various Uzbek and English media texts, focusing on culturally specific elements that pose challenges in translation. Examples are drawn from news articles, films, social media, and advertisements to demonstrate the influence of globalization on translation practices. In addition, academic literature from both Western and Uzbek scholars, such as Venuti (1995), Nida (1964), and Baker (1992), as well as Mamajonov (2007) and Ziyodova (2016), is reviewed to ground the analysis in established translation theories. The framework for the study revolves around two key translation strategies: domestication, which adapts foreign content to fit the cultural norms of the target audience, and foreignization, which preserves the source material's cultural distinctiveness.

Globalization has had a profound impact on media translation, particularly in the area of linguistic borrowing, where terms from one language are adopted into another with minimal alteration. This phenomenon is especially evident in English-Uzbek translations, as English has emerged as the dominant global language in technology, business, entertainment, and sports. As a result, many English terms have been integrated into the Uzbek lexicon with little or no modification. While this facilitates communication in some areas, it poses unique challenges for translators when adapting media texts between the two languages.

For instance, in the realms of technology and business, English terms are widely used in Uzbek media without translation. Words like "internet," "startup," "software," and "marketing" have become so ubiquitous in Uzbek that they are rarely altered. "Internet" remains "internet" (интернет), while "startup" is adapted phonetically as "startap" (стартап), reflecting Uzbek phonetic rules but retaining the original English meaning. This linguistic borrowing is common in urban areas where English is prevalent, but in rural Uzbekistan, where English proficiency is lower, the use of such terms may cause confusion. Here, translators face the challenge of whether to retain the borrowed terms to maintain global relevance or replace them with local equivalents that may resonate better with the audience but risk sounding archaic or obscure.

Similarly, entertainment and pop culture reflect the influence of globalization through linguistic borrowing. Global trends from music, films, and social media have introduced English terms like "viral," "trending," and "influencer" into everyday Uzbek media. For example, "viral" is used as "viral" (вирл) in Uzbek, showing how digital communication and entertainment spaces have blurred the lines between languages. Additionally, in Uzbek media covering Western cultural phenomena, literal translations often fall short of conveying the cultural context. For example, the English "red carpet" is translated as "qizil gilam" (қизил гилам), which retains the literal meaning but may not evoke the same imagery for an Uzbek audience unfamiliar with Western celebrity culture.

Sports media is another domain where linguistic borrowing is prevalent. Terms like "penalty," "offside," "goalkeeper," and "corner kick" are often retained in their English forms when translated into Uzbek. "Penalty," for instance, is commonly used as "penalti" (пеналти), which simplifies communication but might alienate non-English-speaking Uzbek audiences. Global sports events like the Olympics or the FIFA World Cup frequently introduce English terminology that further embeds global language into local media coverage, creating tension between international standardization and local understanding.

Although linguistic borrowing simplifies the translation of global media content, it can also undermine the cultural and linguistic uniqueness of the target language. This is particularly evident in cultural references and idiomatic expressions. For instance, the English idiom "It's raining cats and dogs" does not translate well into Uzbek. A direct translation would confuse the audience, as the association of animals with rain is absent in Uzbek culture. Instead, a more culturally relevant expression like "Shalola bo'lib yomg'ir yog'di" (It rained like a waterfall) must be used to convey the intensity of the rain. This example demonstrates the intricate decisions translators must make when handling linguistic borrowing in the context of cultural translation.

The analysis reveals that the tension between domestication and foreignization is a recurring challenge in media translation. Translators must decide whether to adapt foreign content to local norms (domestication) or retain foreign elements to preserve authenticity (foreignization). Advancements in technology, particularly in machine translation tools like Google Translate, have further complicated this process. While these tools can speed up translation, they often fail to capture cultural nuances, idiomatic expressions, and deeper context. This limitation underscores the essential role of human translators in ensuring culturally appropriate media content.

Additionally, translating content that holds deep cultural significance, such as festivals, historical references, and cuisine, remains a challenge in globalized media. For instance,

translating "Navro'z," the Persian New Year celebrated in Uzbekistan, into English requires not only linguistic translation but also a cultural explanation. Similarly, American holidays like Thanksgiving cannot simply be translated into Uzbek without contextualizing the historical and familial importance of the event.

Globalization has significantly reshaped media translation between Uzbek and English, particularly through linguistic borrowing, cultural adaptation, and the integration of technology. While it has facilitated communication and cross-cultural exchange, it has also posed challenges, such as maintaining cultural authenticity and balancing domestication with foreignization. The role of human translators remains crucial in ensuring that translations not only bridge language barriers but also convey cultural nuance, something that current technology struggles to achieve. As global media consumption continues to rise, the demand for culturally sensitive translations will only grow, reinforcing the importance of cultural literacy in media translation.

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